

Research Question Context

Fraud monitoring and prevention are the most challenging and costly financial businesses. For example, in 2018, \$24.26 Billion was lost due to payment card fraud. Banks and financial houses try to reduce fraud by investing much money in software development. The United States leads as the most credit fraud-prone country, with 38.6% of reported card fraud losses in 2018. (Shiftprocessing, 2022) Analyzing the features of the transactions using machine learning like the logistic regression model could statistically significantly identify the fraudulent transactions, and the study results could be used as proof of concept to develop applications in the future for fraud monitoring and prevention.

Newly released Federal Trade Commission data shows that consumers reported losing more than \$5.8 billion to fraud in 2021, an increase of more than 70 percent over the previous year. (FTC.gov 2022)

Machine learning can be a powerful and influential tool in one of the most challenging and restricted sectors and will drive to increasing the trust for more safe transactions and more financial revenue.

Research Question

The Financial houses and Banks are still looking for tools to monitor and prevent fraud, and at the same time looking to measure the accuracy, efficiency, and effectiveness that could be summarized in one research question: "To what extent can transactions be identified as a fraud?"

Justification

The research question covers the financial houses' and banks' actual needs and determines if the transactions could identify as fraud. This research question covers both requirements: the ability and accuracy of the same question. The research results that will answer the research question will provide the details that will help the decision-maker use the research model as a proof of concept. The research question presents the opportunity to the data analytics and data researcher to compare the results, like comparing the predicted data with the test data to define if the model can identify the fraudulent transactions and to what extent.

Hypothesis

The research hypothesis will be: "Fraudulent transactions can statistically significantly be identified from the provided dataset." The research will evaluate if it can statistically significantly identify fraud transactions. The evidence will be collected to confirm or reject the hypothesis from the logistic regression model as one of the machine learning models. The model evaluation will determine if the thesis can be validated or rejected.

Data Collection

Data Description

Finding a dataset for the historical financial transactions was not easy, including the necessity to answer the research question; any data related to the financial sector is hard to find. The dataset must include enough transactions to train and test the model. Some of the included transactions must be classified as fraud to be healthy data for training the model. The transaction features should identify the fraud transaction characteristics and properties and include a dependent variable that will train the model by labeling or classifying the fraud or non-fraud transactions. The research will use a dataset in a CSV file format named "Fraud Detection Classification" downloaded from Kaggle.com, covering all needed requirements. The dataset is available to the public, does not include any restriction data, includes 101613 transactions(rows) and ten columns. The dataset is a sample and an excellent example of answering the research question and analyzing the transactions. (Kaggle, 2022)

The dataset display "Cash Out" and "Transfer" are only transaction types in the fraud scope.

Advantage and Disadvantage of the used methodology

The advantage of looking for datasets and working with public data allows the data scientist to find a non-restricted dataset and data like what they need to use in the initial research studies, build models, and improve the ability to increase the learning curve and build a proof of concepts. It will help to answer the research questions before using a restricted dataset whet requires authorization to use.

The Disadvantage is the leak of control, the limited number of available variables, and the number of observations in the dataset. Maybe regarding the domain business, the financial sector is confidential, which causes fewer variables and observations. Furthermore, working with an un-trusted dataset, which the researchers could use to build initial models, cannot entirely rely on it.

Challenges

The challenges are related to finding, studying, understanding the data in a dataset that covers all the necessary to answer the research question. For example, to answer the research question, the dataset should include

- Enough variables with types able to work with that types.
- Enough number of observations.
- The dependent variable will use as labels to classify the transactions.

The variables' names and descriptions were challenges to understand the business behind.

Finding an easy source like CSV to collect data from is a challenge, influential, and will reduce the time for the research project.

In [43]: `!pip install -r requirements.txt`

```
Requirement already satisfied: numpy in c:\users\fadyy\anaconda3\lib\site-packages
(from -r requirements.txt (line 1)) (1.19.5)
Requirement already satisfied: pandas in c:\users\fadyy\anaconda3\lib\site-packages
(from -r requirements.txt (line 2)) (1.0.3)
Requirement already satisfied: stats in c:\users\fadyy\anaconda3\lib\site-packages
(from -r requirements.txt (line 3)) (0.1.2a0)
Requirement already satisfied: pytz>=2017.2 in c:\users\fadyy\anaconda3\lib\site-pac
kages (from pandas->-r requirements.txt (line 2)) (2021.1)
Requirement already satisfied: python-dateutil>=2.6.1 in c:\users\fadyy\anaconda3\li
b\site-packages (from pandas->-r requirements.txt (line 2)) (2.8.1)
Requirement already satisfied: six>=1.5 in c:\users\fadyy\anaconda3\lib\site-package
s (from python-dateutil>=2.6.1->pandas->-r requirements.txt (line 2)) (1.15.0)
```

In [44]:

```
import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
pd.set_option('display.max_columns', None)
from scipy import stats
import statsmodels.api as sm
from statsmodels.stats import diagnostic as diag
from statsmodels.stats.outliers_influence import variance_inflation_factor
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from IPython.display import Image
from IPython.core.display import HTML
import seaborn as sns
from scipy.stats import weibull_min
import matplotlib as mpl
from sklearn import linear_model
from sklearn.linear_model import LinearRegression
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
from sklearn.metrics import mean_squared_error, r2_score, mean_absolute_error
from pandas.plotting import scatter_matrix
from sklearn.linear_model import LogisticRegression
from sklearn.metrics import classification_report, confusion_matrix, \
precision_score, accuracy_score, recall_score, f1_score
```

Data Preparation

In [45]:

```
# Load the data set.
df = pd.read_csv(r"fraud_dataset_example.csv")
df.head()
```

Out[45]:

	step	type	amount	nameOrig	oldbalanceOrg	newbalanceOrig	nameDest	oldbalar
0	1	PAYMENT	9839.64	C1231006815	170136.0	160296.36	M1979787155	
1	1	PAYMENT	1864.28	C1666544295	21249.0	19384.72	M2044282225	
2	1	TRANSFER	181.00	C1305486145	181.0	0.00	C553264065	
3	1	CASH_OUT	181.00	C840083671	181.0	0.00	C38997010	

	step	type	amount	nameOrig	oldbalanceOrg	newbalanceOrig	nameDest	oldbalar
4	1	PAYMENT	11668.14	C2048537720	41554.0	29885.86	M1230701703	

In [46]:

```
df.describe()
```

Out[46]:

	step	amount	oldbalanceOrg	newbalanceOrig	oldbalanceDest	newbalanceDe
count	101613.000000	1.016130e+05	1.016130e+05	1.016130e+05	1.016130e+05	1.016130e+05
mean	8.523457	1.740901e+05	9.071753e+05	9.234992e+05	8.810428e+05	1.183998e+06
std	1.820681	3.450199e+05	2.829575e+06	2.867319e+06	2.399949e+06	2.797761e+06
min	1.000000	3.200000e-01	0.000000e+00	0.000000e+00	0.000000e+00	0.000000e+00
25%	8.000000	1.001659e+04	0.000000e+00	0.000000e+00	0.000000e+00	0.000000e+00
50%	9.000000	5.338541e+04	2.019047e+04	0.000000e+00	2.105800e+04	5.178343e+04
75%	10.000000	2.124984e+05	1.947150e+05	2.192178e+05	5.919217e+05	1.063122e+06
max	10.000000	1.000000e+07	3.893942e+07	3.894623e+07	3.400874e+07	3.894623e+07

In [47]:

```
df.info()
```

```
<class 'pandas.core.frame.DataFrame'>
RangeIndex: 101613 entries, 0 to 101612
Data columns (total 11 columns):
#   Column                Non-Null Count  Dtype
---  -
0   step                  101613 non-null  int64
1   type                  101613 non-null  object
2   amount               101613 non-null  float64
3   nameOrig              101613 non-null  object
4   oldbalanceOrg        101613 non-null  float64
5   newbalanceOrig       101613 non-null  float64
6   nameDest              101613 non-null  object
7   oldbalanceDest       101613 non-null  float64
8   newbalanceDest       101613 non-null  float64
9   isFraud               101613 non-null  int64
10  isFlaggedFraud       101613 non-null  int64
dtypes: float64(5), int64(3), object(3)
memory usage: 8.5+ MB
```

In [48]:

```
df_after_drop = df.drop(['nameOrig', 'nameDest', 'isFlaggedFraud', 'step'], axis = 1)
```

In [49]:

```
# filter data
df_after_drop = df_after_drop[df_after_drop.type.isin(['TRANSFER', 'CASH_OUT'])]
```

In [50]:

```
display(df_after_drop.isnull().any())
```

```
type                False
```

```

amount           False
oldbalanceOrig  False
newbalanceOrig  False
oldbalanceDest  False
newbalanceDest  False
isFraud         False
dtype: bool

```

```
In [51]: df_after_dummies = pd.get_dummies(df_after_drop['type'])
```

```
In [52]: df_after_dummies.head()
```

```
Out[52]:
```

	CASH_OUT	TRANSFER
2	0	1
3	1	0
15	1	0
19	0	1
24	0	1

```
In [53]: df_after_dummies = df_after_dummies.drop(['TRANSFER'], axis = 1)
df_after_dummies = df_after_dummies.astype(float)
df = pd.concat([df_after_dummies, df_after_drop], axis=1)
df = df.drop(['type'], axis = 1)
df.head()
```

```
Out[53]:
```

	CASH_OUT	amount	oldbalanceOrig	newbalanceOrig	oldbalanceDest	newbalanceDest	isFraud
2	0.0	181.00	181.0	0.0	0.0	0.00	
3	1.0	181.00	181.0	0.0	21182.0	0.00	
15	1.0	229133.94	15325.0	0.0	5083.0	51513.44	
19	0.0	215310.30	705.0	0.0	22425.0	0.00	
24	0.0	311685.89	10835.0	0.0	6267.0	2719172.89	

```
In [54]: df.describe()
```

```
Out[54]:
```

	CASH_OUT	amount	oldbalanceOrig	newbalanceOrig	oldbalanceDest	newbalanceDes
count	39999.000000	3.999900e+04	3.999900e+04	3.999900e+04	3.999900e+04	3.999900e+04
mean	0.782770	3.415713e+05	9.725422e+04	5.572949e+04	1.483995e+06	2.180107e+06
std	0.412366	4.872281e+05	3.974548e+05	3.388937e+05	2.971902e+06	3.464998e+06
min	0.000000	1.580000e+00	0.000000e+00	0.000000e+00	0.000000e+00	0.000000e+00
25%	1.000000	9.149671e+04	0.000000e+00	0.000000e+00	5.955050e+04	2.736863e+06

	CASH_OUT	amount	oldbalanceOrg	newbalanceOrig	oldbalanceDest	newbalanceDes
50%	1.000000	1.952752e+05	7.000000e+00	0.000000e+00	4.010888e+05	9.234983e+00
75%	1.000000	3.642478e+05	3.491356e+04	0.000000e+00	1.405626e+06	2.432076e+00
max	1.000000	1.000000e+07	1.633313e+07	1.379606e+07	3.173869e+07	3.894623e+00

In [55]:

```
df.info()
```

```
<class 'pandas.core.frame.DataFrame'>
Int64Index: 39999 entries, 2 to 101612
Data columns (total 7 columns):
#   Column          Non-Null Count  Dtype
---  -
0   CASH_OUT        39999 non-null   float64
1   amount          39999 non-null   float64
2   oldbalanceOrg   39999 non-null   float64
3   newbalanceOrig  39999 non-null   float64
4   oldbalanceDest  39999 non-null   float64
5   newbalanceDest  39999 non-null   float64
6   isFraud         39999 non-null   int64
dtypes: float64(6), int64(1)
memory usage: 2.4 MB
```

In [56]:

```
#The bivariate visualizations
scatter_matrix(df, alpha=0.4, figsize=(20, 20), diagonal='hist');
plt.show()
```


Analysis: Logistic Regression

In [57]:

```
#Initial Model.
y = df['isFraud']
x = df.drop(['isFraud'], axis = 1)
Xc = sm.add_constant(x)
logistic_regression = sm.Logit(y,Xc)
fitted_model = logistic_regression.fit()
fitted_model.summary()
print(fitted_model.summary())
```

Optimization terminated successfully.
Current function value: 0.012565
Iterations 18

Logit Regression Results

```
=====
Dep. Variable:          isFraud    No. Observations:          39999
Model:                  Logit      Df Residuals:              39992
Method:                 MLE        Df Model:                   6
Date:                   Tue, 10 May 2022    Pseudo R-squ.:            0.3667
Time:                   12:37:23          Log-Likelihood:           -502.59
```

converged:	True	LL-Null:	-793.62			
Covariance Type:	nonrobust	LLR p-value:	1.725e-122			
=====						
	coef	std err	z	P> z	[0.025	0.975]

const	-2.3331	0.179	-13.070	0.000	-2.683	-1.983
CASH_OUT	-1.8518	0.209	-8.877	0.000	-2.261	-1.443
amount	-2.755e-05	3.3e-06	-8.356	0.000	-3.4e-05	-2.11e-05
oldbalanceOrig	3.152e-05	3.33e-06	9.460	0.000	2.5e-05	3.81e-05
newbalanceOrig	-4.436e-05	3.98e-06	-11.139	0.000	-5.22e-05	-3.66e-05
oldbalanceDest	-1.51e-07	3.62e-07	-0.417	0.677	-8.6e-07	5.58e-07
newbalanceDest	-7.097e-07	2.54e-07	-2.792	0.005	-1.21e-06	-2.12e-07
=====						

Possibly complete quasi-separation: A fraction 0.56 of observations can be perfectly predicted. This might indicate that there is complete quasi-separation. In this case some parameters will not be identified.

In [58]:

```
# calculate the correlation matrix
corr = x.corr()

# display the correlation matrix
display(corr)

# plot the correlation heatmap
sns.heatmap(corr, xticklabels=corr.columns, yticklabels=corr.columns, cmap='RdBu')
```

	CASH_OUT	amount	oldbalanceOrig	newbalanceOrig	oldbalanceDest	newbalanceDest
CASH_OUT	1.000000	-0.572691	-0.008074	0.030248	-0.115575	-0.205923
amount	-0.572691	1.000000	0.070470	-0.031659	0.169870	0.316745
oldbalanceOrig	-0.008074	0.070470	1.000000	0.937968	-0.002125	0.004655
newbalanceOrig	0.030248	-0.031659	0.937968	1.000000	-0.004798	-0.009822
oldbalanceDest	-0.115575	0.169870	-0.002125	-0.004798	1.000000	0.930920
newbalanceDest	-0.205923	0.316745	0.004655	-0.009822	0.930920	1.000000

Out[58]:

<AxesSubplot:>

In [59]:

```
# define two data frames one before the drop and one after the drop
Xc_before = Xc
Xc_after = Xc.drop(['oldbalanceDest'], axis = 1)

# the VFI does expect a constant term in the data, so we need to add one using the a
X1 = sm.tools.add_constant(Xc_before)
X2 = sm.tools.add_constant(Xc_after)

# create the series for both
series_before = pd.Series([variance_inflation_factor(X1.values, i) for i in range(X1
series_after = pd.Series([variance_inflation_factor(X2.values, i) for i in range(X2.

# display the series
print('VIF before drop')
print('-'*100)
display(series_before)

print('VIF after drop')
print('-'*100)
display(series_after)
```

VIF before drop

```
-----
const          9.677898
CASH_OUT       1.498805
amount         1.888247
oldbalanceOrg  9.162569
newbalanceOrig 9.110573
oldbalanceDest 8.627221
newbalanceDest 9.327418
dtype: float64
VIF after drop
```

```
-----
const          9.667309
CASH_OUT       1.498301
amount         1.725966
```

```

oldbalanceOrg    9.157679
newbalanceOrig   9.106352
newbalanceDest   1.115937
dtype: float64

```

```

In [60]: # calculate the correlation matrix after reduce
corr = Xc_after.corr()

# display the correlation matrix
display(corr)

# plot the correlation heatmap
sns.heatmap(corr, xticklabels=corr.columns, yticklabels=corr.columns, cmap='RdBu')

```

	const	CASH_OUT	amount	oldbalanceOrg	newbalanceOrig	newbalanceDest
const	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN
CASH_OUT	NaN	1.000000	-0.572691	-0.008074	0.030248	-0.205923
amount	NaN	-0.572691	1.000000	0.070470	-0.031659	0.316745
oldbalanceOrg	NaN	-0.008074	0.070470	1.000000	0.937968	0.004655
newbalanceOrig	NaN	0.030248	-0.031659	0.937968	1.000000	-0.009822
newbalanceDest	NaN	-0.205923	0.316745	0.004655	-0.009822	1.000000

Out[60]: <AxesSubplot:>


```

In [61]: # Final Model
logistic_regression = sm.Logit(y,Xc_after)
fitted_model = logistic_regression.fit()
fitted_model.summary()
print(fitted_model.summary())

```

```

Optimization terminated successfully.
Current function value: 0.012567
Iterations 21

```

Logit Regression Results

```

=====
Dep. Variable:          isFraud  No. Observations:      39999
Model:                 Logit    Df Residuals:          39993
Method:                MLE     Df Model:              5
Date:                  Tue, 10 May 2022  Pseudo R-squ.:        0.3666
Time:                  12:37:24    Log-Likelihood:        -502.68
converged:              True     LL-Null:               -793.62
Covariance Type:      nonrobust  LLR p-value:          1.658e-123
=====

```

	coef	std err	z	P> z	[0.025	0.975]
const	-2.3348	0.179	-13.080	0.000	-2.685	-1.985
CASH_OUT	-1.8543	0.209	-8.890	0.000	-2.263	-1.445
amount	-2.762e-05	3.3e-06	-8.375	0.000	-3.41e-05	-2.12e-05
oldbalanceOrg	3.166e-05	3.32e-06	9.528	0.000	2.51e-05	3.82e-05
newbalanceOrig	-4.471e-05	3.91e-06	-11.429	0.000	-5.24e-05	-3.7e-05
newbalanceDest	-7.955e-07	1.55e-07	-5.129	0.000	-1.1e-06	-4.91e-07

```

=====

```

Possibly complete quasi-separation: A fraction 0.56 of observations can be perfectly predicted. This might indicate that there is complete quasi-separation. In this case some parameters will not be identified.

```

In [62]: #Cross-validation
X_train, X_test, y_train, y_test = train_test_split(Xc_after, y, test_size=0.20, ran

```

```

In [63]: #Evaluation model
clf = LogisticRegression()
clf.fit(X_train, y_train)
y_pred = clf.predict(X_test)
print(classification_report(y_pred, y_test))

print('Accuracy Score: ' + str(accuracy_score(y_pred, y_test)))

print('Precision Score: ' + str(precision_score(y_pred, y_test)))

print('Recall Score: ' + str(recall_score(y_pred, y_test)))

print('F1-Score: ' + str(f1_score(y_pred, y_test)))

```

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
0	1.00	1.00	1.00	7972
1	0.83	0.54	0.65	28
accuracy			1.00	8000
macro avg	0.92	0.77	0.83	8000
weighted avg	1.00	1.00	1.00	8000

```

Accuracy Score: 0.998
Precision Score: 0.8333333333333334
Recall Score: 0.5357142857142857
F1-Score: 0.6521739130434783

```

```

In [64]: cm = confusion_matrix(y_pred, y_test)
fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(5, 5))

```

```

ax.imshow(cm)
ax.grid(False)
ax.xaxis.set(ticks=(0, 1), ticklabels=('Predicted 0s', 'Predicted 1s'))
ax.yaxis.set(ticks=(0, 1), ticklabels=('True 0s', 'True 1s'))
ax.set_ylim(1.5, -0.5)
for i in range(2):
    for j in range(2):
        ax.text(j, i, cm[i, j], ha='center', va='center', color='red')

plt.show()

```


Extra Machine Learning models outside the research

```

In [65]: #Data Without reduce:
#Cross-validation work based on original selected columns
X_train, X_test, y_train, y_test = train_test_split(x, y, \
                                                    test_size=0.20, random_state=210)

```

Random Forest

```

In [66]: #Import Random Forest Model
from sklearn.ensemble import RandomForestClassifier

#Create a Gaussian Classifier
clf=RandomForestClassifier(n_estimators=100)

#Train the model using the training sets y_pred=clf.predict(X_test)
clf.fit(X_train, y_train)

```

```

Out[66]: RandomForestClassifier()

```

```

In [67]: y_pred=clf.predict(X_test)

```

```

acc2 = accuracy_score(y_test, y_pred)
prec2 = precision_score(y_test, y_pred)
rec2 = recall_score(y_test, y_pred)
f12 = f1_score(y_test, y_pred)
print(classification_report(y_pred, y_test))
print('Accuracy:%0.4f'%acc2, '\nPrecision:%0.4f'%prec2, \
      '\nRecall:%0.4f'%rec2, '\nF1-score:%0.4f'%f12)

```

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
0	1.00	1.00	1.00	7988
1	0.61	0.92	0.73	12
accuracy			1.00	8000
macro avg	0.81	0.96	0.87	8000
weighted avg	1.00	1.00	1.00	8000

Accuracy:0.9990
 Precision:0.9167
 Recall:0.6111
 F1-score:0.7333

In [68]:

```

cm = confusion_matrix(y_pred, y_test)
fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(5, 5))
ax.imshow(cm)
ax.grid(False)
ax.xaxis.set(ticks=(0, 1), ticklabels=('Predicted 0s', 'Predicted 1s'))
ax.yaxis.set(ticks=(0, 1), ticklabels=('True 0s', 'True 1s'))
ax.set_ylim(1.5, -0.5)
for i in range(2):
    for j in range(2):
        ax.text(j, i, cm[i, j], ha='center', va='center', color='red')

plt.show()

```


Decision Tree Classifier

```
In [40]: # Import Decision Tree Classifier
from sklearn.tree import DecisionTreeClassifier
dt = DecisionTreeClassifier()

# Train Decision Tree Classifier
dt = dt.fit(X_train, y_train)
```

```
In [41]: #Predict the response for test dataset
y_pred_dt = dt.predict(X_test)

acc3 = accuracy_score(y_test, y_pred_dt)
prec3 = precision_score(y_test, y_pred_dt)
rec3 = recall_score(y_test, y_pred_dt)
f13 = f1_score(y_test, y_pred_dt)
print(classification_report(y_pred_dt, y_test))
print('Accuracy:%0.4f'%acc3, '\nPrecision:%0.4f'%prec3, '\nRecall:%0.4f'%rec3, \
      '\nF1-score:%0.4f'%f13)
```

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
0	1.00	1.00	1.00	7979
1	0.67	0.57	0.62	21
accuracy			1.00	8000
macro avg	0.83	0.79	0.81	8000
weighted avg	1.00	1.00	1.00	8000

```
Accuracy:0.9981
Precision:0.5714
Recall:0.6667
F1-score:0.6154
```

```
In [42]: cm = confusion_matrix(y_pred_dt, y_test)
fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(5, 5))
ax.imshow(cm)
ax.grid(False)
ax.xaxis.set(ticks=(0, 1), ticklabels=('Predicted 0s', 'Predicted 1s'))
ax.yaxis.set(ticks=(0, 1), ticklabels=('True 0s', 'True 1s'))
ax.set_ylim(1.5, -0.5)
for i in range(2):
    for j in range(2):
        ax.text(j, i, cm[i, j], ha='center', va='center', color='red')

plt.show()
```



```
return str({ 'isFraud': isFraud })
```

```
tran = { 'CASH_OUT': 0.0, 'amount': 181.0, 'oldbalanceOrg': 181.0, 'newbalanceOrig':  
isFraudTran(tran)}
```

Out[33]: "{ 'isFraud': 1}"

In []:

Summary of Implications

The data analysis succeeded in building a machine learning classification model using Logistic Regression and evaluation model to answer the research question "To what extent can transactions be identified as a fraud?" based on the current dataset. The data analysis results rejected the research hypothesis "Fraudulent transactions can statistically significantly be identified from the provided dataset." based on the evaluation model evidence and the current dataset. The evaluation model results were around 99% Accuracy score as a general for all transactions. However, the other evidence, like Precision score, which represents the quality of model results, was 83%, Recall score, which represents the number of true positives, was 53%, and F1-score, which describes the model performance, was just 65%. The model's low performance and quality are because of the low number of predicted fraud transactions, which the logistic regression model's success to predict as true positive. The results come less than Financial houses and Banks' expectations and acceptance levels. Financial transactions need more effective tools to monitor and prevent fraud, and the model is not an excellent practical tool to diagnose fraud transactions.

Limitation of Analysis

The major limitation of the data analysis is the data availability. For example, a current dataset has a limited number of transaction features, just ten columns, a limited number of rows of 101613 transactions. After filtering the data to select the transactions in the fraud scope, the number of rows reduces to 39999 rows and the limitate number of the actual fraud transactions in the dataset. It looks like more transaction features and actual fraud transactions in the dataset could improve the model performance and prediction quality. Moreover, the Logistic Regression is a classic machine learning model and needs extra tools and techniques to handle issues like multicollinearity and overfitting. Recommended Course of action The data analysis results support doing more research using more data. More transactions rows, more transactions features, and more transactions flagged as fraud will help the model run multiple times with more different data, get more training, and improve the model performance and quality of predictions. Compare the results with other classification machine learning models like Random Forest or Decision-Tree models. The financial houses and Banks looking for more

effective and efficient solutions to monitor and prevent fraudulent transactions will not accept the current model performance and quality results.

Two Directions for the Future Study

The first direction is the most classic direction, which is related to the data analysis research nature and the current research, which is looking for more data to train and improve the model performance and quality. The data may be more transactions, and some flagged as fraud. More transaction features, usually the public data is just for prove concepts. However, when the results support starting data analysis projects for business proposals, the chance to collect more data with more quality will be better. The project and research will become more productive if the data analyst can collect the data.

The second direction is to compare the results for the current research model with other classification machine learning models. Like the Random Forest and Decision-Tree, the different models include more enhancement to handle the common issues like multicollinearity and overfitting. Maybe the other models will be an excellent choice to perform the research, answer the research question, and confirm the hypothesis. The current research code file includes an extra section to evaluate and compare the results with two different machine learning models. Random Forest and the Decision-Tree, both models, display better quality around 100% and better performance around 76%, could improve with more training by more data and meet the Financial houses and Banks acceptance.

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